

ICAO Circular 344 Guidelines on Education, Training and Reporting of Fume Events

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KEYWORDS

fume events, crew member exposure, awareness raising, circular

ABBREVIATIONS

AMTs Aircraft maintenance technicians

ABSTRACT

The ICAO published Circular 344 “Guidelines on education, training and reporting practices related to fume events” at the end of 2015. The scope of the guidance is limited to education, training and reporting of fume events by flight crew, cabin crew, and aircraft maintenance technicians (AMTs). In addition, the management should also receive the basic training. The idea is to enable crews and AMTs to prevent, recognize and respond to the presence of fumes/odour. The circular does not address occupational health issues. The overall content of the circular was presented at the conference.

At the 38th session of the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) General Assembly, the International Transport Workers’ Federation (ITF) and the International Federation of Air Line Pilots’ Associations (IFALPA) invited the Technical Commission to consider the flight safety implications of crew member exposure to oil fumes/odor sourced to the aircraft air supply system. ITF and IFALPA also requested the ICAO Council to develop guidance material to improve awareness and training of flight crew, cabin crew, and AMT related to the management of fume events.

As a result of this work, an ICAO Circular 344 “Guidelines

on education, training and reporting practices related to fume events” was published at the end of 2015. Notable is, that the scope of the guidance is limited to education, training and reporting of fume events by flight crew, cabin crew, and aircraft maintenance technicians (AMTs). This enables them to prevent, recognize and respond to the presence of fumes/odor. The circular does not address occupational health issues; nor does it address on board exposure to smoke or fire.

The Circular is divided into six different chapters, see below. Introduction and Basic Education is aimed for all stakeholders, including the management (flight crew, cabin crew, AMTs, and management). As each aviation professional group (i.e. flight crew members, cabin crew members, AMTs) has a specific role in recognizing and responding to fumes, particularly to those that are air supply system-sourced, a group-specific training is provided to them. One important chapter is on reporting of fume events, and this includes an example of the reporting form. Finally, there is a chapter for AMTs on trouble shooting, and a short chapter on investigation.

Chapter 1. Introduction

Chapter 2. Basic education

- For all the stakeholders (pilots, cabin crew, maintenance, management)

Chapter 3. Training

- Group specific training, i.e. parts for pilots, cabin crew and AMTs

Chapter 4. Standardized reporting

- An example of reporting fume is presented

Chapter 6. Event Investigation

- Basic description of the issues to be considered in the fume event investigation

The aim of the circular is to enhance flight safety through raising awareness of fume events as well as training on how to cope with such an event.